

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

**REGIONAL
MAPS**

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INTRODUCTORY REMARKS

By Andrea Membretti & Jussi P. Laine

The Horizon 2020 project MATILDE - Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance Integration and Local Development in European Rural and Mountain Regions - aims to examine the impact of migration on local development and territorial cohesion. The project pays special attention to European rural and mountainous regions, which have thus far remained under-studied among the global migration trends. While the transition from a mainly rural to a predominantly urban society constitutes one of the most important transformations in the contemporary world, the developments and impacts of migration flows outside urban areas have also increased in significance but remain inadequately understood. Furthermore, the specific needs of rural and mountainous regions have rarely been considered in formulating the governance of migration. If unaddressed, the sentiments of people in 'places that don't matter' risk fuelling an authoritarian dynamic that rejects diversity altogether.

MATILDE's focus seeks to challenge the common depiction of migration as yet another burden for already marginalised or peripheral territories by providing a balanced analysis of the impacts of migration on local development. The project moves from the hypothesis that immigration can act as a driver of social and economic development in the medium and long term, especially in remote areas, where immigration counterbalances processes such as depopulation and economic decline. Migration to rural and mountainous areas can play an important role for European rural regions, among other things by contributing to the revitalising of the social and economic local milieu, reducing territorial inequalities, and reconfiguring urban-rural interconnections. It may trigger the revitalisation of abandoned spaces, generating new demand and stimuli for services of general interest that affect urban-rural/mountain relationships. Migration may be a crucial element in attaining balanced territorial development as defined in the UN Sustainable

Development Goals. Place-based policies and adequate governance measures are needed to avoid the existing risk that migration flows exert a negative impact on socioeconomically and geographically fragile areas.

The project starts from the premise that 'place matters' (Massey 1994; Gieryn 2000; Dreier et al. 2014), and that it is the result of continuous sociocultural negotiation. Such negotiation processes involve territorial structures and various categories of inhabitant - old and new, temporary and permanent, nationals and foreigners (Membretti & Viazzo 2017). Geographical, structural, and socio-territorial aspects influence the impact migration can have on society and the economy. These aspects further make the difference in migrants' settlement process, affecting the quantitative and qualitative impact of migration processes on such territories. MATILDE emphasises the multi-causal nature of migration, understanding migration processes as ongoing negotiations of mobility and immobility (Halfacree & Rivera 2012) in which aspirations and abilities to migrate or to stay are addressed as crucial (Carling & Schewel 2017). MATILDE considers place attachment processes

and the resulting intention to stay a prerequisite for migrants' prompting of long-term transformation and inducing of sustainable impacts in rural and mountainous places. We explicitly address the multiple attachments associated with translocal identities and belonging, because they may foster the territorial/social exchange and innovations that often occur within these circular movements of people and ideas.

MATILDE develops and tests a transdisciplinary conceptual and methodological framework for a multidimensional assessment of the economic and social impacts of Third Country Nationals (TNCs). The project uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, adopting an action-research approach that emphasises the agency of migrants and the site-specific features of the regions involved. To assess such impacts and processes, MATILDE is conducting 13 case studies in different regions across Europe. The case studies have been selected based on the presence of urban poles, variously interconnected with rural and mountainous areas via flows of people, economic resources, and cultural

exchange. We hope the MATILDE activities will contribute to improving the knowledge of the social and economic development potential of TCNs in rural and mountainous areas. They will help to understand the mechanisms behind the socioeconomic integration of TCNs and provide policymakers, practitioners, and local stakeholders with analytical tools and place-based solutions/policy recommendations to counteract misperceptions and untap the migration potential in rural and mountainous regions.

THE ROLE OF RURAL AND MOUNTAINOUS AREAS FROM A REGIONAL EUROPEAN PERSPECTIVE

Regions - as institutions between state and local administrations - have assumed a leading role in the process of European integration in the recent past. In the 1990s important developments and several optimistic predictions accompanied the 'Europe of the Regions' perspective (Borras-Alomar et al. 1994), in which the main avenues of EU policy, in seeking to overcome territorial inequalities, favoured an active role for these intermediate

bodies within the 'multi-level governance approach' (Conzelmann 1998; Amin & Thrift 1995; Piattoni 2009).

However, despite the importance of the regions in the construction of the European Union, as well as in its functioning, the 2000s witnessed a progressive reduction in their role, as European institutions directed attention away from these territorial actors (Caciagli 2011). This is particularly true of rural and mountainous regions. Despite relevant European policies and the economic support given to rural and mountainous regions, the sense of being on the margins of economic and social policy is increasingly strong in these areas. As Rodríguez-Pose (2017) states, many European regions have long felt left behind, or that they do not matter. It is no coincidence that disaffection with European institutions in these territories is spreading, populism is growing, and xenophobia and movements inspired by sovereignism are emerging.

We should not forget that half the European land mass is classified as predominantly rural, and about 30 per cent

as mountainous. More than a quarter of the EU population lives in rural areas. The marginalisation of rural and mountainous regions is even more objectionable if we consider Article 174 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, which states that the EU will strengthen economic, social, and territorial cohesion within it, in particular by ‘reducing disparities between the levels of development of the various regions and the backwardness of the least favoured regions’. It goes on to state that ‘[a]mong the regions concerned, particular attention shall be paid to rural areas, areas affected by industrial transition and regions suffering from severe and permanent natural or demographic handicaps, such as the northernmost regions with very low population density and island, cross-border and mountain regions.’

The role rural and mountainous regions can play in Europe’s shared wealth and wellbeing is clear. The agricultural production, forests, water reserves, cultural heritage, diversity, languages, and local autonomy in these areas make them irreplaceable. Furthermore, in the face of the radical changes brought by the Covid-19 pandemic,

what these regions have to offer in terms of differing modes of settlement, production, and consumption is likely to be increasingly sought after, because their local systems are characterised by less anthropic pressure and more circular economies. As densely populated urban areas were hit hardest by the pandemic, the social rarefaction of these regions connotes welcome resilience in such times of crisis.

IMMIGRATION AS A POTENTIAL FOR AND THREAT TO REGIONS LEFT BEHIND

MATILDE’s vision stems from the potential of rural and mountainous regions. Our aim is to improve our shared knowledge base and awareness of best practice to co-construct a Europe that leverages this tremendously underutilised heritage, a pool of resources that must feed the progress of our entire continent and not drift towards forms of local micro-protectionism. In analysing the potential of these regions, immigration is one of the fundamental factors that must be considered (Perlik et al. 2019). Rural and mountainous areas have been structurally losing inhabitants for decades; they suffer from

chronic labour shortages and an increasingly ageing population, since young people often move to cities, while other rural and mountainous regions are performing relatively well, both socially and economically.

Naturally, the arrival of new inhabitants is a fundamental resource when national and local policies are implemented to govern it. Today immigration, especially international immigration from non-European countries (but also intra-EU and interregional immigration), is the main contribution to the demographic stability of marginalised regions, as well as a crucial factor in the functioning of entire sectors of local economies, from agriculture to tourism, personal services to small and medium-sized industries and crafts. It also has a major impact on housing and the reconversion of underused local real estate (Membretti & Lucchini 2018). MATILDE investigates this phenomenon to understand how much it weighs on the development of rural and mountainous regions without reducing it to a study of foreigner integration processes or the identification of new policies that favour only newcomers.

If policies are to be sound, we must also acknowledge and address the challenges. To alleviate the pressures felt by both local populations and immigrants, applicable and well-functioning policies for the inclusion of newcomers, and public spaces of encounter and negotiation between cultures and needs, are required. Equally important is the right of local populations to preserve their own traditions compared to those of 'outsiders'. The main aim of this project, and the reason it is implemented by a network in which local actors have as much weight as scientific ones, is to understand how immigration, in all its forms but especially from non-EU countries, affects the overall development of these regions. MATILDE involves rural and mountainous European regions through a participatory reflection on their capacity for resilience, and their creative adaptation to current and future challenges.

MATILDE develops an assessment of the socioeconomic impact of Third Country Nationals to put one of the continent's greatest resources at the centre of European public discourse: rural and mountainous areas and those

who live in them, whether by birth, choice, necessity, force, or a combination of reasons. The project contributes to the construction of a new Europe, one whose focus is has shifted to the inhabitants that do not matter, based not on their passport but on their geographical and territorial location.

* * *

This booklet presents cartographic representations created for each of the regions covered by MATILDE, providing visual representations of the salient features of the regions under scrutiny. Migration is undoubtedly a highly mediated phenomenon (Georgiou & Zaborowski 2017; Laine 2019). It is through media that we encounter the turbulent world surrounding us, inform ourselves, experience feelings, produce judgements, react to the pains and atrocities experienced by others, and are sometimes even moved to action (Kotilainen 2016). However, the message we get from the media is not always impartial, but only an interpretation of the reality (Laine 2019). A narrative that spectacularises and

simplifies migration has become dominant in the European public sphere (Laine 2019; 2020a). Over the years, the repetition of its inherent cartographic structure across all kinds of institutional documents has turned its visual composition into the 'normal' cartographic representation of migration in the EU (van Houtum & Bueno Lacy 2019). How migration phenomena are represented, especially through the massive use of images, often privileges the emergency frame related to sea landings and undocumented migrants, while obscuring the diversity of migration processes that take place in a given territory (Musarò & Parmeggiani 2014). The emergency frame presents the migration situation as an unprecedented crisis necessitating a security response (Laine 2020a), fuelling a perception of immigration as a threat to our 'national' societies, and thus as something to be fought against (Laine 2020b), overshadowing the alternative framings of migration as a potential resource for local development in the process.

Framing involves the social construction of a phenomenon and influences an individual's perception of it. The

collective process of the social construction of reality (Berger & Luckman 1966) is communication about reality; how it is perceived, rather than what it is. It is a construction (and reconstruction/redefinition) of and through images, which are the condensation of identities, the symbol of places and the main medium of communication itself. In this process the distinction between 'reality' and the image of reality is difficult to sustain. If a situation is represented by images, and thus visually perceived, as real, the observable consequences of this definition will be real, i.e. the representation will be of a performative nature (Membretti 2009). In this age of visual information, we are effectively persuaded to (mis)perceive reality through various visual representations; our sense of reality is increasingly affected by visual representations and content. Visual representations thus contribute to the construction of their objects, by which these meanings are increasingly linked to the images that convey them. How people perceive reality has a number of implications for their opinions, attitudes, and behaviour, through which misperceptions can act as impediments to social change. Among visual

aids maps can especially be considered one of the most alluring and persuasive descriptions of world politics (Kwan 2004). They are not merely a reflection of power but of power itself: visual statements and narratives about the topics they picture, or in other words, visual discourses (van Houtum and Bueno Lacy 2020).

The maps presented here represent the territory and its dynamics based on scientific evidence. At the same time they offer a multifaceted perspective of the represented 'object'. To provide visual representations of migration grounded in sound quantitative data, it is crucial to stimulate collective rethinking and a shared visualisation of the impact of migration on European rural and mountainous regions. With this in mind the maps provided in this booklet, based on data collected in the primary part of the MATILDE project, provide accurate information about the territorial characteristics of the regions in focus, the distribution of third-country nationals within them, and their sociodemographic characteristics. We consider this collection of maps an input for stimulating reflection and discussion at the local level, through the involvement of

local stakeholders, of the multi-layered impact and diverse presence of TCNs in MATILDE regions. We thus hope to raise a new collective awareness of the territorial dimensions of migration while co-producing a new representation of the reality with the local stakeholders - that is a different narrative - through images (too).

We wish to recall two main aspects that emerge from this cartography and that will guide the consultation about the maps. First, the maps presented in this booklet show the significant degree of diversity in MATILDE regions in spatial and territorial characteristics. In line with Woods and McDonagh (2011) the 'rural' cannot be addressed as static, but is instead subject to constant change and transformation, fostered by immigration and wider processes of globalisation and mobility. The MATILDE rural and mountainous regions have been selected based on their diversity in terms of the spatial dimension (location and border dimension); various institutional and legal

systems (migration regimes and the degree of regional autonomy); physical and geographical characteristics; migration history; and finally, socioeconomic performance. This local diversity affects their capacity to attract and integrate (or not) TCNs, as well as their ability to exploit the full potential of a foreign presence to support local development. Identifying and assessing the site-specific features and contextual factors of each region is therefore extremely relevant to the study of migration processes from a territorial perspective. Second, the MATILDE regions also encompass a significant variety of migration profiles. The maps provided in this booklet show the heterogeneity in terms of share, development, and sociodemographic profiles of the TCNs living in the MATILDE regions. This initial overview is an open invitation to dig more deeply into the broad range of migration processes taking place in rural and mountainous areas across Europe.

MAPS

MAP 1 MATILDE REGIONS

The MATILDE regions are spread across Europe. Four regions are in Northern Europe - in Finland, Sweden, and Norway. Two regions are in Western Europe - both in Scotland (UK). Seven regions are in Central Europe - five in Germany, and two in Austria. The Southern European regions border South Tyrol and Turin in Italy, and Huesca in Spain, as well as the Turkish region of Bursa. Bursa, Finnish Ostrobothnia, and the Scottish regions of North Ayrshire and the Outer Hebrides represent coastal regions. Finally, the region of Haskovo in Bulgaria is the only region in the Balkans. The MATILDE regions have very unequal dimensions. The smallest region, Berchtesgadener Land in Germany, occupies only 1.6% of the area of the largest - Innlandet in Norway.

MAP 2 SHARE OF POPULATION LIVING IN RURAL AREAS

The MATILDE regions are mainly rural or semi-rural, meaning that every other inhabitant lives in a rural area. There are also some relevant exceptions.

Finnish North Karelia and Ostrobothnia, and the Swedish Dalarna and Norwegian Innlandet are predominately rural regions. In the United Kingdom, the Outer Hebrides are predominately rural. In North Ayrshire, the island of Arran is rural, while the mainland is intermediate (20-50% of its population live in rural areas). In Germany and Austria, the MATILDE regions are rural or intermediate, with the exception of Vorarlberg, which has a large urban portion.

In Southern Europe the regions are quite diverse. In Huesca (ES) 20 to 50% of the population live in rural areas, but this proportion is higher in South Tyrol (Italy), where one in two people live in rural areas. Two regions are predominantly urban (less than 20% of the population live in rural areas) - Turin (Italy) and Bursa (Turkey). Finally, in the Balkans, the region of Haskovo (Bulgaria) is intermediate, with between 20-50% of the local population living in rural areas.

MAP 3 MOUNTAIN REGIONS BY TOPOGRAPHY AND POPULATION

The MATILDE regions are mainly mountainous. In the southern regions of Bursa in Turkey and South Tyrol in Italy more than half the population live in mountainous areas. Turin (Italy) and Huesca (Spain) are also predominantly mountainous, but most of the population (> 50%) lives in non-mountainous areas. This is also the case for the Austrian and German regions, with the exception of Neustadt (Aisch)-Bad Windsheim in Central Germany.

In the North the MATILDE regions in Finland and Sweden are non-mountainous, while the Norwegian region of Innlandet is mountainous. In Scotland the only predominantly mountainous area is the Island of Arran in North Ayrshire. Similarly, in the Balkans, the region of Haskovo is predominantly non-mountainous.

MAP 4 BORDER REGIONS

Most MATILDE regions are located by state borders. This is the case for Finnish North Karelia on the border with Russia; and Swedish Dalarna and Norwegian Innlandet, which are adjacent to each other on the Swedish-Norwegian border.

Other border regions are Spanish Huesca and Italian Turin (adjacent to the French border), and South Tyrol (on the Italo-Austrian border). Similarly, Vorarlberg and Carinthia in Austria are on the borders with Slovenia and Switzerland respectively. The three Southern German regions are on the Austrian border, while Regen is adjacent to the Czech Republic.

Other MATILDE regions include coastal regions - Ostrobothnia in Finland, the Outer Hebrides and North Ayrshire in Scotland, and Bursa in Turkey. The central German region of Neustadt (Aisch)-Bad Windsheim is neither a border nor a coastal region.

**MAP 5 VORARLBERG:
DEGREE OF URBANISATION**

Map 5 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Austrian province of Vorarlberg. The region is predominantly rural, but urban areas (towns and suburbs) dominate in the west (the Rhine Valley).

MAP 6 VORARLBERG: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 6 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Austrian province of Vorarlberg. Residents of the most populous areas in the Rhine Valley can generally reach a hospital within a 15-minute drive. Although the northern part of the region has a significant number of inhabitants, these residents need up to 30 minutes to reach the nearest hospital.

**MAP 7 CARINTHIA:
DEGREE OF
URBANISATION**

Map 7 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Austrian province of Carinthia. Most of the territory is occupied by rural areas. Klagenfurt am Wörthersee is the only city area in the region. Towns and suburbs are mainly found in the centre and eastern half of the province. They surround the district capitals.

**MAP 8 CARINTHIA:
TRAVEL TIME TO
HOSPITAL**

Carinthia

Travel time to hospital by car 2016

Light blue	1 - 15 min
Light blue	16 - 30 min
Medium blue	31 - 45 min
Dark blue	46 - 60 min
Very dark blue	61 - 90 min
Dark blue	91 - 120 min
Very dark blue	121 - 180 min

Population

Small red dot	1 - 20
Small red dot	21 - 100
Small red dot	101 - 500
Small red dot	501 - 1 000
Small red dot	1 001 - 5 000
Small red dot	5 001 - 20 000
Small red dot	20 001 - 107 491

Black outline	MATILDE region
Red hatched box	Other MATILDE region
White box	NUTS 3 region
Thick black line	National border

Sources:
ESPON: Travel times 2016
Eurostat/GISCO:
Population grid 2011, NUTS 3 regions 2016
Cartography: Simo Rautiainen 2021
University of Eastern Finland

Map 8 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Austrian province of Carinthia. Residents of the most populous central areas can generally reach the nearest hospital within a 15-minute drive. Although the eastern territories have a relatively large population, the drive to the nearest hospital takes more time.

MAP 9 HASKOVO: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 9 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Bulgarian province of Haskovo. There is one city area in the western part of the province. There are towns and suburbs in the centre. Rural areas occupy the northern and southern parts of the region.

MAP 10 HASKOVO: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 10 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Bulgarian province of Haskovo. Residents of the most populous areas generally need to drive for between 15 and 30 minutes to reach the nearest hospital. In the less populous north and south, the travel time is longer.

**MAP 11 OSTROBOTHNIA:
DEGREE OF URBANISATION**

Map 11 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Finnish province of Ostrobothnia. There are three urban areas (towns and suburbs): two in the centre and one in the north. Rural areas occupy most of the region.

MAP 12 OSTROBOTHNIA: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Ostrobothnia

Travel time to hospital by car 2016

1 - 15 min
16 - 30 min
31 - 45 min
46 - 60 min
61 - 90 min
91 - 120 min
121 - 180 min

Population

1 - 20
21 - 100
101 - 500
501 - 1 000
1 001 - 5 000
5 001 - 20 000
20 001 - 107 491

	MATILDE region
	Other MATILDE region
	NUTS 3 region
	National border

Sources:
 ESPON: Travel times 2016
 Eurostat/GISCO:
 Population grid 2011, NUTS 3 regions 2016
 Cartography: Simo Rautiainen 2021
 University of Eastern Finland

Map 12 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Finnish province of Ostrobothnia. In general, residents of areas close to the coast have quicker access to hospital. Travel times for islanders and residents of more inland areas are longer.

MAP 13 NORTH KARELIA: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 13 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Finnish province of North Karelia. Rural areas occupy more than half the territory. Urban areas (towns and cities) stretch from north to east, dividing the rural areas in two. Most residents in the urban areas live in the city of Joensuu and town of Lieksa. The remaining parts of these municipalities are scarcely populated.

MAP 14 NORTH KARELIA: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

North Karelia

Map 14 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Finnish province of North Karelia. Residents living in the centre of the region can reach the nearest hospital within 30-45 minutes. Inhabitants living closer to the region's borders need to drive longer, for up to 3 hours in the north-eastern part of the region. North Karelia has one specialised hospital in Joensuu, and several health centres in other municipalities.

MAP 15 BERCHTESGADENER LAND: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 15 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the rural district of Berchtesgadener Land in Germany. Rural areas are found in the western part of the region, and towns and suburbs are in the east. The proportion of urban to rural areas is roughly equal.

MAP 16 BERCHTESGADENER LAND: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 16 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the German rural district of Berchtesgadener Land. Most residents can reach a hospital within a 15-minute drive.

MAP 17 OBERALLGÄU AND GARMISCH-PARTNEKIRCHEN: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 17 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the rural districts of Oberallgäu and Garmisch-Partenkirchen in Germany. In Oberallgäu towns and suburbs are found in the centre of the region, stretching from north to south.

In Garmisch-Partenkirchen the southern part of the region is predominantly urban (towns and suburbs), whereas the north is rural. The proportion of urban to rural areas is roughly equal in both regions.

MAP 18 OBERALLGÄU AND GARMISCH-PARTNEKIRCHEN: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 18 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the rural districts of Oberallgäu and Garmisch-Partenkirchen in Germany. Most residents from both regions can reach a hospital within a 15-minute drive, though Oberallgäu offers easier access to hospitals.

MAP 19 NEUSTADT A.D. AISCH - BAD WINDSHEIM: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 19 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the rural districts of Neustadt a.d. Aisch - Bad Windsheim in Germany. Towns and suburbs are found in the central parts of the regions. Rural areas dominate.

MAP 20 NEUSTADT A.D. AISCH - BAD WINDSHEIM: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 20 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the rural district of Neustadt a.d. Aisch - Bad Windsheim in Germany. Most residents can reach a hospital within a 15-minute drive. Residents in the northern and eastern parts need up to 30 minutes to drive to the nearest hospital.

Neustadt a.d. Aisch – Bad Windsheim

Travel time to hospital by car 2016

Population

Sources:
 ESPON: Travel times 2016
 Eurostat/GISCO:
 Population grid 2011, NUTS 3 regions 2016

Cartography: Simo Rautiainen 2021
 University of Eastern Finland

MAP 21 REGEN: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 21 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the rural district of Regen in Germany. Towns and suburbs are found along the valleys in the central part of the region. Rural areas dominate.

MAP 22 REGEN: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 22 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the rural district of Regen in Germany. Most residents can reach a hospital within a 15-minute drive. Residents in the most central part need to drive for 45 minutes, whereas some residents from the southern part need up to 30 minutes to reach the nearest hospital by car.

**MAP 23 SOUTH TYROL:
DEGREE OF
URBANISATION**

Map 23 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Italian province of South Tyrol. Rural areas dominate. Urban areas are scattered across the region. There is one city in the south, and several towns and suburban areas.

**MAP 24 SOUTH TYROL:
TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL**

Map 24 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Italian province of South Tyrol. The most populous areas offer the quickest access to a local hospital. For most residents the travel time does not exceed 45 minutes, but some areas require a drive of one hour or longer.

South Tyrol

Travel time to hospital by car 2016

- 1 - 15 min
- 16 - 30 min
- 31 - 45 min
- 46 - 60 min
- 61 - 90 min
- 91 - 120 min
- 121 - 180 min

Population

- 1 - 20
- 21 - 100
- 101 - 500
- 501 - 1 000
- 1 001 - 5 000
- 5 001 - 20 000
- 20 001 - 107 491

- MATILDE region
- Other MATILDE region
- NUTS 3 region
- National border

Sources:
 ESPON: Travel times 2016
 Eurostat/GISCO:
 Population grid 2011, NUTS 3 regions 2016
 Cartography: Simo Rautiainen 2021
 University of Eastern Finland

MAP 25 METROPOLITAN CITY OF TURIN: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 25 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Metropolitan City of Turin in Italy. Turin is the only city in the region. Urban areas dominate in the east, and rural areas dominate in the west.

MAP 26 METROPOLITAN CITY OF TURIN: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Metropolitan City of Turin

Travel time to hospital by car 2016

Lightest blue	1 - 15 min
Light blue	16 - 30 min
Medium-light blue	31 - 45 min
Medium blue	46 - 60 min
Dark blue	61 - 90 min
Very dark blue	91 - 120 min
Darkest blue	121 - 180 min

Population

Small red dot	1 - 20
Medium red dot	21 - 100
Large red dot	101 - 500
Very large red dot	501 - 1 000
Large red dot with outline	1 001 - 5 000
Very large red dot with outline	5 001 - 20 000
Large red dot with outline	20 001 - 107 491

Black outline	MATILDE region
Red hatched outline	Other MATILDE region
Grey outline	NUTS 3 region
Thick black line	National border

Sources:
 ESPON: Travel times 2016
 Eurostat/GISCO:
 Population grid 2011, NUTS 3 regions 2016

Cartography: Simo Rautainen 2021
 University of Eastern Finland

Map 26 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Metropolitan City of Turin in Italy. Residents from the more urban eastern areas can drive to a local hospital within 15-30 minutes. For residents from the more rural western part the drive is longer.

MAP 27 INNLANDET: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 27 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Norwegian county of Innlandet. Rural and uninhabited areas dominate. Towns and suburbs are found in the southern part of the region.

MAP 28 INNLANDET: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 28 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Norwegian county of Innlandet. Residents from the urban areas in the south and the rural areas in the north-east have the quickest access to the nearest hospital. For many residents from the other parts of the region, travel time to a hospital exceeds one hour. There are two medical centres that provide basic healthcare services in the western and north-western part of the county. Blank spots indicate missing data from uninhabited mountain areas.

MAP 29 HUESCA: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 29 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Spanish province of Huesca. Rural areas dominate. Towns and suburbs are found in the north and west of the region, and in the south and east. The Pyrenees occupy the northern part of the province, so these areas are mainly mountainous. Plains with farmland occupy the southern part of the province. Some farmland is irrigated.

MAP 30 HUESCA: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 30 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Spanish province of Huesca. The central part of the region offers the quickest access to a local hospital. For residents in the northernmost and southernmost areas, the travel time to a local hospital exceeds 46 minutes. The regional hospital in Huesca is equipped with specialised medical care facilities. There are also two hospitals that offer basic facilities in Barbastro (eastern part) and Jaca (north-western part).

MAP 31 DALARNA: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 31 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Swedish province of Dalarna. Rural areas take up more than half its territory. Towns and suburbs are found in the south and east of the region. There is also one urban area in the centre. This municipality - Mora - includes one small town and a few smaller rural villages. It is thus less urban than the map suggests.

MAP 32 DALARNA: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 32 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Swedish province of Dalarna. Residents from the centre and southeast of the region have quicker access to a local hospital (mostly up to 45 minutes) than residents from the north (more than 90 minutes) and west (mostly 60-120 minutes). Areas with shorter travel time to healthcare facilities are significantly more densely populated than areas with longer travel time.

MAP 33 BURSA: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 33 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Turkish province of Bursa. There are several cities in the centre of the region. Towns and suburbs are located to the north and east of the cities. Rural areas are found in the south and north of the region.

MAP 34 BURSA: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Bursa

Map 34 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Turkish province of Bursa. Residents from the urban areas in the centre have the quickest access (up to 15-30 minutes). Residents from the more rural western part of the region need up to 15-30 minutes to reach the nearest hospital. Although the eastern part of the region is populous, the travel time to the nearest hospital is longer (up to 30-60 minutes). Residents from the south have the longest drive to the nearest hospital.

**MAP 35 NORTH
AYRSHIRE: DEGREE OF
URBANISATION**

Map 35 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Scottish province of North Ayrshire. The mainland consists of town and suburbs, whereas the Isle of Arran is a rural area.

MAP 36 NORTH AYRSHIRE: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 36 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Scottish province of North Ayrshire. Most mainland residents from the south can get to the nearest hospital in up to 15 minutes, whereas most residents from the north need to travel for up to 30-45 minutes. Similarly, on the Isle of Arran there is a local hospital providing both emergency and maternity facilities. Residents from the eastern part of the island can reach it within 15 minutes. The remaining residents need up to 30 minutes. The drive from the island's northern part takes up to 45 minutes. The National Health Service employs visiting professionals for rural hospitals. Hospitals in Glasgow are within a one-hour drive of mainland North Ayrshire.

MAP 37 OUTER HEBRIDES: DEGREE OF URBANISATION

Map 37 illustrates the degree of urbanisation in the Scottish Outer Hebrides. Rural areas dominate on all the islands. Only about 20% of the Outer Hebrides' population lives in the main urban centre - Stornoway on the Isle of Lewis. The remaining 80% lives scattered on the Isle of Lewis and on 14 other inhabited islands.

MAP 38 OUTER HEBRIDES: TRAVEL TIME TO HOSPITAL

Map 38 illustrates the time needed to reach the nearest hospital in the Scottish Outer Hebrides. The largest local hospital is in Stornoway in the north-eastern part of the Isle of Lewis. Travel times to this facility vary from up to 15-30 minutes (for residents from the north) to more than 46 minutes for southern Lewis and the Isle of Harris. The hospital on Benbecula also serves residents from North Uist and South Uist. These islands are connected by bridges, and the travel time does not generally exceed 30 minutes. With drives of up to 15 minutes residents from Benbecula and Barra (in the south) have the quickest access to the nearest hospital. However, Barra does not have emergency or maternity facilities. Consultants from mainland hospitals also provide services at the Western Isles Hospital.

MAP 39 NUMBER AND SHARE OF THIRD-COUNTRY NATIONALS (TCNS)

Map 39 represents the number and share of third-country nationals (TCNs) in MATILDE regions in 2018. Bursa in Turkey and Turin in Italy have the largest numbers of TCN residents (represented as yellow circles). However, Dalarna in Sweden (dark green) has the highest share of TCNs. The regions with the smallest share of TCN populations are North Karelia (Finland), North Ayrshire and the Outer Hebrides (Scotland), and Carinthia in Austria (without Klagenfurt-Villach). For most MATILDE regions the share of TCNs is between 2.6% and 7.5%.

MAP 40 GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF TCNS AND SHARE OF FEMALE TCNS

Map 40 illustrates the gender distribution of TCNs in 2018 and the share of female TCNs between 2008 and 2018. The county of Inlandet in Norway (here marked as Oppland and Hedmark) and the province of North Karelia in Finland have slightly more female than male TCNs. The most visible disproportion between male and female TCNs is observed in the German MATILDE regions (especially in Regen), as well as in Huesca (Spain) and parts of Carinthia.

Between 2008 and 2018 the share of female TCNs increased by 0.1-3.0% in the regions marked in yellow. In regions marked in blue the share of female TCNs decreased.

MAP 41 NET MIGRATION IN MATILDE REGIONS IN 2008-2017

Map 41 illustrates the net migration in MATILDE regions between 2008 and 2017. The data include internal and external migration. MATILDE regions differ in their population development. Regions marked in green gain residents through different types of migration. Dark and medium green indicate the most attractive regions for international migrants. In the four regions marked in yellow more people moved out than in.

MAP 42 POPULATION DEVELOPMENT IN MATILDE REGIONS IN 2008-2018

Map 42 presents the population development in the MATILDE regions as the product of natural change (birth rate) and migration between 2008 and 2018. The first region type has a growing population as a result of both positive natural change and positive net migration. It includes Ostrobothnia (FI), South Tyrol (IT), Reintal-Bondeseegebiet and Bludenz-Bregenzener Wald (AU), and Bursa (TR).

The second region type has a growing population as a result of positive net migration that exceeds negative natural change. This is the case in the Swedish and Norwegian regions, in most German regions (except Regen), in the Austrian region of Klagenfurt-Villach, and in Turin (IT).

The third region type has a decreasing population as a result of negative natural change that exceeds positive net migration. North Karelia (FI), the Outer Hebrides (UK), Regen (DE), and Huesca (ES) belong to this type.

The fifth region type has a decreasing population resulting from both natural and migratory dynamic. This type represents the population development of North Ayrshire (UK), Oberkarnten and Unterkarnten (AU), and Haskovo (BG).

MAP 43 POPULATION DEVELOPMENT IN MATILDE REGIONS IN 2008-2012

The map presents the population development in the MATILDE regions as the product of the natural change and migration between 2008 and 2012.

Compared to the previous map, this older representation of the population development reveals some relevant differences. First, before 2012 the Outer Hebrides (UK) and Huesca (ES) had a growing population as a result of positive net migration that exceeded negative natural change. Second, the Austrian region of Bludenz-Bregenzer Wald had a decreasing population as a result of negative net migration that exceeded the positive natural change. Finally, the German regions of Regen and Neustadt a.d. Aish-Bad Windsheim had a decreasing population as a result of both migratory and natural dynamics.

MAP 44 POPULATION DEVELOPMENT IN MATILDE REGIONS IN 2013-2018

The map presents the population development in the MATILDE regions as the product of natural change and migration between 2013 and 2018. This map therefore covers the most recent period. Focusing on the last available five-year period shows that negative population change patterns have become stronger in the regions of North Karelia (FI), the Outer Hebrides (UK), and Huesca (ES). The population in all these regions is decreasing because of both natural and migratory dynamics. However, this map shows that in recent years all the German regions had increased their population as a result of positive net migration exceeding negative natural change.

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